

BREEDING OF BARBERIS (BERBERIS L) IN UZBEKISTAN

Chorshanbiev F.M.

Tashkent State Agrarian University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13123367>

Abstract. *The article presents the results of research on the scientific study of representatives of the genus *Berberis L* in Uzbekistan, on the selection of plus forms and the creation of new varieties of barberry. There is information about 3 native species of barberry, about the morphology of the berries, about the habitat and growing conditions. In the Western Tien Shan, 10 plus forms of barberry were selected, of which patents were received for 3 promising forms Sijjak-1, Nanay-5 and Sijjak-10 and they were included in the state register of cultivated plant varieties of the Republic of Uzbekistan on April 26, 2024, as new varieties barberry.*

Keywords: *oblong barberry, entire barberry, coin barberry, plus forms, selection of promising forms, barberry variety, state register of cultivated plant varieties.*

Introduction. Today, on a global scale, special attention is being paid to the cultivation of non-traditional berry fruit and shrub-like plants, the fuller use of their food, medicinal and landscape features, and the expansion of the production of natural medicines from them. Among them, barberry is a valuable medicinal plant included in the Pharmacopoeia of European and CIS countries due to its useful properties and practical use.

Berberidaceae is one of the most important representatives of (Berberidaceae Torr. et. Cray). The barberry plant is a source of valuable alkaloids for medicine, it has been determined that about 15 alkaloids are present in the fruits and roots of the black barberry. Medicinal properties of barberry are determined by the amount of vitamins and alkaloids present in its fruit and root.

Abu Ali Ibn Sina used black barberry and red barberry fruit juice to treat liver and gall bladder diseases. “Kiyami zirk” prepared from Black barberry root is widely used in the medicine of the peoples of Central Asia and Afghanistan in the treatment of liver and gall bladder diseases. This drug improves bile secretion, has spasmolytic properties, which means it lowers the tone of the gallbladder and affects the contraction rhythm. This situation improves the secretion of bile, creates conditions for the disappearance of the inflammatory process in the bile ducts and gall bladder. Berberine alkaloid causes bile dilution and reduces the occurrence of bile secretion in the gallbladder. Therefore, barberry drugs are considered an effective tool in the treatment of hepatitis, cholecystitis, biliary tract dyskinesia [5].

Many decorative varieties of ordinary barberry and Thunberg barberry have been created and are widely used in landscaping and landscape design. In 1893, the famous breeder scientist I.V.Michurin [4] was interested, in his opinion, the juice of barberry fruits is a promising raw material of great importance for the food industry. The main goal of the barberry selection carried out by the scientist was to create a seedless barberry variety. To achieve this goal, *Berberis vulgaris* X. B. *Deglinata* was crossed in 4 generations in 1932 to create a seedless variety. The fruits of this barberry variety are large and quick to harvest.

In the following years, barberry was not selected as a fruit plant, only V.Yu.Jilenko [2] carried out selection of primary sources for barberry selection in Russia. As a result of the research the varieties of barberry Appolon, Ermolai, Galina, Tyoma, Donetsk were created.

Barberry fruits are rich in biologically active substances and vitamins, which is why they are used in scientific medicine as a blood-stopping and blood-pressure-lowering agent. In the following years the scope of scientific research is increasing on the cultivation of valuable cypress species such as *V. oblonga*, *B. integerrima*, *B. nummularia*, etc. as medicinal plants in industrial plantations.

Research object and methods. Study of genetic resources of barberry plant and selection of promising forms was conducted in Burchmullo forestry area. Biometric dimensions of fruits and seeds are 0.01 mm using a barbell circle accuracy, weight on the “Pocket Scale” electronic scale is 0.01 g.

Weight of 100 fruits of barberry species and forms, 1 kg. The amount of juice and seed yield, weight of 1000 seeds was determined based on the requirements of GOST 13056.4–67 (QzDSt 322.15.04.2009) “Methods for determining the mass of 1000 seeds”. Evaluation of the selected positive forms according to their economic and biological characteristics was carried out on the basis of a 5-point system based on the requirements of the methodological guide “Program and methodology for studying varieties of fruit, berry and nut crops” (1999).

Based on the results of the complex evaluation of barberries forms according to their valuable economic and biological characteristics, among them, the forms evaluated with more than 4 points according to their valuable economic and biological characteristics were separated as promising forms. As a result of the research work, 10 positive plants of barberries were selected according to valuable economic and biological characteristics. It was noted that the fruits of these selected bushes are large, fertile, the weight of 100 fruits is around 24-41 grams.

Research results and their discussion. In the flora of Uzbekistan, there are 3 of the 8 types of cypress distributed in Central Asia: black barberries (*Berberis oblonga* Rgl), red barberries (*Berberis integerrima* Bge), coin-shaped barberries (*Berberis nummularia* Bge). Barberry species grow mainly in mountainous area, descend along river valleys to low plains of 700-800 m, and create barberry formations in orchards.

Black barberries are widespread in the mountains with moisture-demanding and temperate climate, while red and coin-shaped barberries as a drought-resistant and heat-loving species grows abundantly in rocky-sandy river valleys on the southern mountain slopes Barberry-Berberidaceae Torr.et. Cray. The scientific name of the genus *Berberis* L., included in the family, and the development of the systematics of barberries species are related to the name of K. Linnaeus (1753). For the first time, he included 2 types of barberries - common barberries (*Berberis vulgaris* L.) and krit barberries (*Berberis sretica* L.) in this category. In the 18th century, 5 species of barberries were known to science, and in the 19th century, more than 150 species of barberries were scientifically named and included in the genus *Berberis* L. [1, 3].

Our research has shown that 8 species of barberries are naturally distributed in Central Asia, in particular, 3 in Uzbekistan. These 8 types of barberries distributed in Central Asia are deciduous barberries, and they grow mainly in mountainous areas. Among them, the most common species is the black-eyed barberries (*B. oblonga* Rgl.), which has created many natural barberry groves on the territory of the republics of Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan and Kazakhstan. This species of barberry was first described by Eduard Regel (E. Regel 1877) as the widespread important form of black barberry (*B. heteropoda* Schrenk.)-*V.heteropoda* Schrenk var. *oblong* Rgl. allocated as Later, the systematic Schneider (Schneider 1905) noted that this barberry, widely distributed in Turkestan, is a separate species [5].

Black barberry grows in the form of a large multi-bodied bush, 3-5 m tall, at an altitude of 1300-2800 m above sea level. The leaves are thin, ovate, inverted ovate and elliptic, 2-6 cm long, with straight or toothed edges, dark green on top and green on the bottom. Branches are round, new 1-2-year-old branches are reddish, perennial branches are covered with gray bark. The branches have single and three-piece spines, 0.5-1.5 cm long, and the middle spine is always longer than the side spines. The inflorescence is complex, multi-flowered with 10-30 (50) flowers, each of which has a diameter of up to 1 cm and consists of 6 yellow-lemon petals [1].

Blooms in May and ripens in September. Fruits are dark red, turning into black-blue berries when fully ripe. The fruits are covered with an indistinct white powder. Berries are also produced in bunches, each bunch contains 8-25 berries, weighing 0.17-0.25 g, length 9.7-10.4 mm, diameter 4.5-5.6 mm., the shape is oblong-elliptic. The berry is 2-seeded, the seed is oblong, brown, shiny, has a strong shell. Seed weight 0.01-0.04 g, length 5.1-6.2 mm, diameter 2.1-2.8 mm. 1000 seeds weigh around 13-16 g. 1 kg contains 51-52 thousand seeds. Large-fruited hybrids of this barberry occur spontaneously in nature, the weight of 100 fruits of which is recorded to be 38-45 grams.

Figure 1. Black barberis (*Berberis oblonga*) fruits

The area of black barberis is limited to Western Tyan-Shan and Pamir-Aloy, this species grows in Piskom, Ugom, Chotkal, Qorjantov, Kurama, Turkestan, Hisar, Zarafshan ridges, Central Tyan-Shan, Fergana and Aloy ridges.

Red barberis – *Berberis integerrima* Bge was first separated by Bunge (Bunge 1843) and included in the genus. In nature, it is a large multi-bodied bush growing up to 4 meters. The flowers are 0.3-0.9 cm in diameter, the flower band is 1.0-1.2 cm long. The petals are the same, yellow, 6 pieces. 17-24 berries are formed in one flower cluster and they ripen in September in dark red color.

Fruit length 9-10 mm, diameter 4.2-6.0 mm, weight 0.16-0.22 g. The shape of the fruit is oblong-elliptic, sometimes ovoid. The berry has 1-2 seeds, the seeds are oblong, brown in color, 5.2-7.2 mm long, 2.3-3.5 mm in diameter, 0.01-0.03 g in weight. The weight of 1000 seeds is about

15-16 g. 1 kg contains 65-66 thousand seeds. This species is found in the Pamirs in the valleys of the Panj, Vanch, and Yagnob rivers, in the Darvaz, Hisar, Turkestan, and Zarafshan mountain ranges, in the Western Tian Shan, Piskom, Ugom, and Qorjantov mountain ranges. Outside of Central Asia, it is also found in the mountainous part of Iran, in the mountains of Jungor and Kashghar.

Table 1

Morphological description of fruits and seeds of barberis species

Indicators	Types of barberis			
	Coin-shaped barberis Berberis nummularia)	Red barberis (Berberis integgerima)	Black barberis (Berberis oblonga)	B. oblonga large fruit form
Fruit length, mm.	-	9,0±0,13	9,9±0,04	12,1±0,15
Fruit diameter mm.	6,3±0,04	5,5±0,10	5,1±0,04	7,7±,0,13
Fruit weight g.	0,1±0,00	0,2±0,01	0,2±0,003	0,5±0,02
Weight of 100 fruits, g.	14-15	16-20	17-23	38-45
The number of fruits in one bunch, pcs	24-38	17-24	8-28	8-12
Average number of seeds per fruit, pcs	2,2±0,03	2,0±0,12	2,1±0,08	2,5±0,08
Seed length, mm.	4,3±0,07	6,0±0,13	5,7±0,04	6,8±0,09
Seed diameter, mm.	3,2±0,13	2,9±0,07	2,4±0,03	3,4±0,05
Average seed weight, g.	0,01±0,001	0,2±0,001	0,02±0,001	0,03±0,001
Weight of 1000 seeds, g.	11-12	15-16	13-16	18-23
Seed yield from 1 kg of fruit, %	24-28	20-24	20-22	18-20
Juice yield from 1 kg of fruit, %.	72-75	65-72	60-70	55-68

Coin-shaped barberis– *Berberis nummularia* Bge., Bunge (Bunge 1843) first included it in the series in 1843. 3-4 m high, multi-bodied bush. The leaves are fleshy, ovate, 2.8-3.5 cm long, 1.7-1.8 cm wide. The branches have a diameter of 3-4 cm and are covered with thorns 2-3 cm long. Inflorescence consists of 15-25 flowers, flowers 0.8-0.9 in diameter, 6 petals, yellow color.

The fruits are pinkish red, showy, and ripen at the end of September. One fruit bunch contains 24-38 spherical berries. One fruit is 5.9-6.8 mm in diameter, weighs 0.09-0.13 g, and contains 1-3 seeds. The seeds are light-brown, small, 4.5-5.0 mm long, 3.0-3.5 mm in diameter, 0.01-0.02 grams in weight. 1000 seeds weigh 7-8 g. In 1 kg of seeds, their number is 131-132 thousand.

This species has a very decorative appearance when it fruits, a bush covered with bright red-pink, red fruits, which stand out from afar on the hillsides and are kept on the bush for a long time. The range of this species covers Tien-Shan, Pamir-Aloy. Apart from Central Asia, it is found in the mountainous regions of Iran.

Figure 2. Red barberry (*Berberis integerrima*) fruits

As a result of the research conducted on the study of the genetic resources of the barberries plant and the selection of promising forms in the Burchmullo forestry area, 10 plus bushes of the barberries were selected according to the valuable economic and biological characteristics. It was noted that the fruits of these selected bushes are large, fertile, the weight of 100 fruits is around 24-41 grams.

As a result of the morphological and biochemical study of selected barberries fruits, 10 positive barberries bushes were selected from among them for the first time, and 3 promising forms were isolated from them: Sijjak-1 (coin-shaped barberries), Nanay-5 variety (red barberries), Sijjak-10 (black barberries) varieties and was obtained and registered as a patent in the State Register of Plant Varieties of the Republic of Uzbekistan on 26.04.2024. Below is a description of the new barberries varieties:

“Sijjak-1” variety. Coin-shaped barberry (*B.nummularia*,) is a fruitful bush, 1.-2 meters high, with an average yield of 1.4 kg. Fruits are reddish pink, spherical, $5.9+0.05$ mm in diameter. 100 berries weigh 14.5 grams. 73.5% juice can be obtained from 1 kg of fruit. 1000 seeds weigh 11.5 grams. The content of vitamin C in berries is 131, 27 mg/100 grams. The second decade of September is the time when the fruits are fully ripe. Depending on the productivity, a 5-year-old bush yields from 0.5 kg to 2.2 kg. Dried fruits are used as a spice. Juices can be made from wet fruit. Fruit taste -4.3 points, growth period 150 days. The overall rating of the variety is 4.3 points.

“Nanay-5” variety. It was isolated from a promising form of the red barberis (*B.integgerima*) species. The height of the bush is 3.3 meters, the average yield is 1.4 kg. The fruit is red, oblong, 10.2+0.07 mm long, and 100 berries weigh 31.4 grams. 65% juice can be obtained from 1 kg of wet fruit. The weight of 1000 seeds is 32.1 grams. The amount of vitamin C in the fruit is 117.38 mg/100g. The period of full fruit ripening is the second decade of September. Depending on the productivity, 0.3-2.4 kg can be harvested from a 5-year-old bush. Juice can be obtained from wet fruits. Fruity taste - 4.4 points. The overall rating of the variety is 4.5 points.

“Sijjak-10” variety. Black barberis is a shrub of the barberry (*B. oblonga*) type, a large-fruited and fruitful shrub, 2.5 meters high, with an average yield of 1.2 kg. The berry is dark blue-black, covered with white dust, 11.9+0.14 mm long. The weight of 100 fruits is 41.5 grams. The juice yield from 1 kg of fruits is 64%. The weight of 1000 seeds is 20.5 grams. Berries contain 151,650 mg/100 g of vitamin C. Ripening of fruits is considered to be the middle of September. It was noted that the yield of a 4-year-old bush is from 0.4 to 2.2 kg. The wet fruit juice can be used as a harmless coloring agent in the food and wine industries. Fruit taste - 4.5 points. The overall rating of the variety is 5 points.

Conclusion: 1. 8 types of barberis distributed in the republics of Central Asia (*B.oblonga*, *B.heteropoda*, *B.integgerima*, *B.nummularia*, *B.sibirica*, *B.kaschgarica*, *B.crataegina*, *B.densiflora*) 3 of them (*B.oblonga*, *B.integgerima*, *B.nummularia*) can be noted that they are found in the flora of Uzbekistan and that they are distributed naturally in mountainous areas.

2. As a result of the morphological and biochemical study of selected barberry fruits, 10 positive barberry bushes were selected from among them for the first time, and 3 promising forms were isolated from them: Sijjak-1 (coin-shaped barberis), Nanay-5 (red barberis), Sijjak-10 (black barberis) varieties were patented and registered in the state register of plant varieties of the Republic of Uzbekistan on 26.04.2024.

REFERENCES

1. Бердиев Э.Т., Чоршанбиев Ф. Биоразнообразие рода *Berberis* L. В Центральной Азии. //Сохранение и устойчивое использование биоразнообразия плодовых культур и их диких соородичей: Материалы Международной научно-практической конференции 23-26 августа 2011г. –Ташкент, 2011.– С. 66-71.
2. Жиленко В.Ю. Создание исходного материала для селекции барбариса (*Berberis*L) в условиях юго-запада ЦЧР: Автореферат дисс...канд. биол. наук. (Белгород. Гос.нац. исслед. университет) –Рамонь, 2011.–20 с.
3. Запрягаева В.И. Дикорастущие плодовые Таджикистана–М.: Л.: Наука, 1964–695 с.
4. Мичурин И.В. Барбарис бессемянный //Сочинения. –Москва-Ленинград 1941, Том 4.– С.334-336.
5. Чоршанбиев Ф.М. Зирк (монография).–Тошкент, ЎзР ФА Минитипографияси, 2018.– 120 б.